

Best Practice: Organization and Editing of Texts - The Principle of separating Content and Format

Anyone who has ever created a lengthy document is probably familiar with the following problems: You are currently writing something or copying elements, but the text editing software always moves the texts, tables or graphics to places where they do not belong, or they are displayed incorrectly. When you finally complete your document with all its contents and send it to another person in the same format, it may be that it is displayed differently on their computer. There are numerous reasons for this, e.g. the use of different word processing software, different additional packages or another operating system.

Separating content and layout of a document can help in such a situation. In order to offer an alternative to the systems using the WYSIWYG principle (What You See Is What You Get), new solutions have been developed over the past decades that are based on the WYSIWYM principle (What You See Is What You Mean) instead. Here you define text modules for certain tasks, e.g. chapter heading, table, list or body text, and the software takes care of the formatting using a given template. Almost all web applications work according to this principle today. The browser uses markup language, e.g. HTML, to read the textual content, while the actual formatting of the text and the design of the website is done in CSS. Other markup languages, which are used on MediaWiki pages or code repositories, work similarly.

L^AT_EX

For scientific work, LaTeX has established itself as a widely used software package, which also follows the WYSIWYM principle. The generated layout of LaTeX documents is considered clean and is particularly powerful when dealing with formulas and graphics. Due to its modular functional structure and the outsourcing of content to different files, it is well-suited for collaborations. The application is considered very reliable and is therefore often used for extensive work such as diploma theses and dissertations, where strict typographic guidelines must be observed. LaTeX is particularly popular in the MINT disciplines, with their standardized formulas and diagrams.

Another aspect of latex (but also other applications based on the WYSIWYM principle) is that you are practically "forced" to organize your data correctly. Since the .tex file itself consists only of text, other media such as images or vector graphics must be saved separately, which requires a good folder structure. The proprietary BIN formats of other applications (such as Microsoft Office, LibreOffice etc.) allow media to be saved within the document. There, however, they are usually compressed and are difficult to export separately. The separate storage of the respective media makes it easier to find them again and the use of predominantly open formats means that the file can be reused more easily later on.

Nevertheless, many are skeptical of LaTeX and similar applications and continue to use mostly classic text editing programs. The reason for this is the steep learning curve, which makes getting started difficult. First, the syntax must be learned and understood, various software packages installed and, if necessary, a template for the desired document created. This can act as a deterrent for people without an IT or technical background. Furthermore, many people are used to seeing the result of the work immediately, without having to laboriously compile the files. In order to remedy this, several services such as Overleaf (also known as ShareLaTeX) have been established, which compile LaTeX documents with colleagues in real time and have the result displayed in a separate window. Nevertheless, the initial hurdle mentioned above remains.

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Creation of all text media with LaTeX - an interview with Nathalie Lang

At the Chair of Media Security at the Bauhaus University Weimar, LaTeX is used for almost all text-based media. Doctoral student Nathalie Lang has been working in media security for almost 2 years and has told us about her experience with the software package.

Even before she started her bachelor's degree at the University of Duisburg-Essen, there was a preparatory course in computer science that dealt with LaTeX, among other things. The LaTeX-enthusiased tutors managed to spark Nathalie's interest in the software. As a result, she not only wrote her bachelor's and master's thesis using the typesetting system, but also voluntarily took notes and documents with it. Fortunately, all colleagues at the Chair of Media Security, where she now works, are also very adept at LaTeX. Presentations, academic papers, exercise sheets and other media are all created with LaTeX in this group. This means that in the commonly shared chair-repository for text documents one can usually only find the .tex files to be compiled as needed.

To Nathalie, the fundamental advantage of LaTeX is that it can be used to process almost all text-based documents. This makes conventional software such as Microsoft Word, PowerPoint or Publisher unnecessary since you can create everything with one application. In contrast to the common editing programs, many of which are also proprietary, LaTeX is based on the open-source principle. On the one hand, it is very well-documented, on the other hand there is a large community that is constantly developing new packages and extensions, actively answering questions in numerous Internet forums and thus paving the way for beginners.

What Nathalie particularly appreciates about LaTeX is that it compiles everything as it was previously defined. So if an output does not look the way it should, it is not because of the poor usability of the text editing program, but because of incorrectly worded definitions or commands. Once you have put enough time and effort into a LaTeX document, you will be rewarded with a template that you can reuse at any time without much effort.

Finally, Nathalie also mentions various advantages in relation to her work. LaTeX can handle source directories and references well which is useful, since many portals for scientific media already offer the download of sources in BibTeX format as a standard. However, LaTeX really stands out when dealing with graphics. The software does not only represent mathematical equations exceedingly well, but also creates and edits algorithms as vector graphics since usually only certain small names have to be changed.

LaTeX Code:

```
\begin{equation}
x^2 = \frac{y}{\sqrt{z^3}} (\sin 3x)
\end{equation}
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Output:

$$x^2 = \frac{y}{\sqrt{z^3}} (\sin 3x)$$

If you have any questions about LaTeX or the WYSIWYM principle, please contact Mr. Kevin Lang, Research Data Management Contact Point at the Bauhaus University Weimar (kevin.lang@uni-weimar.de).

Do you have any questions about this Best Practice or would you like to suggest another one?

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